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This brief examines the governance of health sector public-private partnerships (PPPs) in the Sindh province of Pakistan, where outsourcing has expanded without corresponding institutional oversight. This analysis identifies critical capacity gaps within the Department of Health's (DoH's) existing PPP oversight unit and weak accountability in managing PKR 98.8 billion (US\$ 352.7 million) in health contracts.

An assessment of reform options found that strengthening the existing oversight structure is more feasible than establishing a new autonomous entity. We recommend enhancing institutional capacity through specialized recruitment and monitoring frameworks, strengthening service delivery via evidence-based planning, and improving quality through regulatory collaboration and performance-based contracting. These reforms would improve healthcare efficiency and outcomes for Sindh's 55.7 million residents.

INTRODUCTION

In Pakistan, PPPs have emerged as a key strategy for expanding healthcare access. Under Pakistan's 18th Constitutional Amendment, health service delivery has been devolved to provinces, leading to diverse approaches in service delivery. In Sindh, the country's second most populous province with 55.7 million people, the DoH has increasingly turned to PPPs to manage healthcare facilities and deliver essential services.

Pakistan's health sector PPPs encompass both traditional contracting and tailored institutional arrangements specific to the country's legal framework. While conventional PPPs involve contracts with private healthcare providers and non-governmental organizations (NGOs), PPPs in Pakistan also increasingly use "Section 42 companies" – not-for-profit entities established that can receive public funding while maintaining operational autonomy from government bureaucracy. These companies, such as PPHI Sindh (formerly known as People's Primary Healthcare Initiative), represent a hybrid model that aims to combine public sector accountability with private sector efficiency in healthcare delivery.

This brief analyzes the current governance landscape of health sector PPPs in Sindh and presents recommendations for institutional reform. Through review of legal frameworks, institutional arrangements, and existing contracts, it examines two potential reform paths: establishing a new autonomous entity or strengthening the existing PPP Node – a dedicated unit within the DoH responsible for identifying, preparing, implementing, and managing PPP projects in the health sector. Based on this analysis, the brief provides specific recommendations for the DoH to improve its governance around outsourcing.

CURRENT STATE OF PPP GOVERNANCE IN SINDH

The governance of health sector PPPs in Sindh operates through a complex institutional framework established by the 2010 Sindh PPP Act. This framework includes the PPP Policy Board, chaired by the Chief Minister, which approves projects; the PPP Unit within the Finance Department, which appraises and finances projects; and sector-specific PPP Nodes, including one within the DoH, responsible for identifying, preparing, implementing, and managing PPP projects in the province. This structure emerged following

Pakistan's 18th Constitutional Amendment in 2010, which devolved health service delivery to provinces, giving them greater autonomy in healthcare management.

There are three distinct management streams for PPPs in Sindh’s health sector – the PPP Node, PPHI Sindh, and single-line grants – each operating under different rules and oversight mechanisms.

This fragmentation complicates effective performance management and ensuring value for money across the health system. Table 1 provides an overview of budget allocations to these three streams for fiscal year (FY) 2023-24.

Table 1. Overview of Grants Allocated to PPPs Under Sindh’s Current Health Budget in Fiscal Year 2023/24

Entity	Original Budget (PKR Million)	Modified Budget (PKR Million)	% of Total Current Health Budget
PPP Node	768.5	2,159.0	0.98%
PPHI Sindh	12,762.6	16,008.6	7.25%
Single-Line Grants*	69,137.9	80,645.1	36.5%

Source: Information Management Unit - Finance GoS, 2024

**Single-line grants are lump-sum transfers allowing recipients discretion over internal allocation. While PPHI Sindh also receives single-line grants, we list it separately due to its significant role in primary healthcare delivery in Sindh.*

The PPP Node has a formal mandate to oversee health sector PPPs but currently manages only 2% of total PPP funds and lacks the technical capacity to do so effectively. Despite its intended central governance role, the Node's actual oversight is limited to a small portfolio of PPP arrangements worth PKR 2.2 billion (US\$ 7.7 million). PPHI Sindh and other single-line grant recipients – representing 98% of total health sector PPPs - operate outside its purview. In addition, current staffing consists primarily of non-technical civil servants without specialized expertise in contract management, procurement, or health systems (Aga Khan University, 2020). The Node has no dedicated legal or financial specialists, limiting its ability to design

and monitor complex healthcare contracts. Performance monitoring relies largely on self-reported data from contractors, with limited independent verification or systematic evaluation of outcomes. It also lacks specialized expertise in project design, contract management, and performance monitoring. Additionally, review of the Node's budget for FY 2023-24 indicates a mismatch between its operating budget and its responsibilities: for every rupee in PPP funds the Node directly oversees (PKR 2.2 billion or US\$ 7.7 million in total), it has only one cent to cover its salary and operating expenses (PKR 28.8 million or US\$103,000 total).

PPHI Sindh, managing over half of the province's PHC facilities, operates under a governance structure that provides limited accountability. The five-year, non-binding Memorandum of Understanding between PPHI Sindh and the DoH involves single-line budget transfers without robust performance management mechanisms. Our analysis of current arrangements showed no systematic linking of funding to service delivery outcomes or quality metrics. This accountability gap is particularly significant given PPHI Sindh's annual budget of PKR 16.0 billion (US\$ 57.1 million) in FY 2023-24.

The system of single-line grants, representing PKR 80.6 billion (US\$ 287.9 million) annually, operates with minimal performance oversight. These grants, provided to various private entities (14%), and public-sector and autonomous healthcare institutions (86%), lack standardized monitoring mechanisms and clear performance expectations. The absence of structured performance metrics makes it difficult to assess the effectiveness of these substantial investments or to identify areas needing improvement.

Recognizing these challenges, the DoH has initiated reform through its Plan of Action for Strengthening PPPs (2021-26). This strategic document provides a framework for addressing governance gaps and improving the effectiveness of health sector partnerships (see Box 1).

Box 1. Sindh Health Department's Plan of Action for Strengthening PPPs: 2021-26 (Department of Health, 2021)

To enhance healthcare delivery in Sindh through PPPs, the action plan adheres to the following guiding principles:

- 1. Strengthening the quality of health service delivery.*
- 2. Promoting value for money.*
- 3. Ensuring equitable access to healthcare for the poor and underserved populations.*
- 4. Encouraging local and sustainable solutions.*
- 5. Harnessing the private health sector to achieve Universal Health Coverage (UHC) and SDG3 targets.*
- 7. Upholding transparency and accountability in PPPs and healthcare contracting.*

Vision

To improve the health of Sindh's population by ensuring universal access to affordable, high-quality healthcare through collaboration with the private sector.

Objectives

- 1. Strengthen the capacity of the Sindh DoH to manage and oversee PPPs and healthcare contracting, focusing on primary healthcare as a step toward achieving UHC and health-related SDG targets.*
- 2. Enhance the performance of existing PPP arrangements to improve the quality and affordability of healthcare under the Pakistan/Sindh Essential Health Services Package, prioritizing underserved communities.*

Strategic Pillars

- 1. Governance and Capacity Building: Enhance institutional capacity for contract management, policy formulation, and robust monitoring systems.*
 - 2. Service Delivery Strengthening: Expand access to essential healthcare services by engaging with private sector providers, with a focus on primary healthcare and underserved populations.*
 - 3. Quality and Performance Management: Drive quality improvements through performance-based financing, standardized benchmarks, and independent monitoring mechanisms.*
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OPTIONS FOR REFORM

ThinkWell conducted a systematic assessment of Sindh's PPP governance options through documentary analysis, stakeholder consultation, and comparative review. Our methodology included examination of legal frameworks and existing contracts; consultations with DoH officials, current PPP operators, and regulatory bodies; and analysis of PPP models from other Pakistani provinces and international contexts. We evaluated two potential reform paths—establishing a new

autonomous entity or strengthening the existing PPP Node —against three criteria crucial for Sindh's context: implementation feasibility within existing constraints, alignment with the DoH's strategic priorities, and potential for rapid improvement in governance outcomes.

Option 1: Establishing a new autonomous entity

Establishing a new autonomous entity for health PPP governance would create a dedicated institution with greater operational flexibility but require extensive legislative and institutional development. This approach would follow Khyber Pakhtunkhwa's Health Foundation model, established through the KP Health Foundation Act 2016. Creating a similar entity in Sindh would require passing comparable legislation – a process demanding significant political capital and administrative resources.

The primary advantage of an autonomous entity lies in its potential to overcome the bureaucratic constraints inherent in government departments.

A dedicated health foundation could adopt more flexible operational policies, particularly for recruitment and procurement, enabling it to attract and retain specialized technical expertise that government structures often cannot accommodate. These advantages could prove particularly valuable in addressing the technical capacity gaps identified in Sindh's current PPP governance arrangements.

An autonomous entity would allow for clearer separation between strategic oversight and operational management. This structural distinction enables more effective governance by clearly defining roles for policy direction versus implementation. Patouillard et al. (2007) highlight such a separation as a key factor in effective public-private engagement, particularly for maintaining appropriate focus on health equity and quality while pursuing operational efficiencies.

This governance model could also better insulate technical decisions from short-term political pressures. By establishing clear accountability mechanisms through board representation and performance agreements, an autonomous entity would maintain public accountability and provide the operational stability needed for consistent contract management. This structure may support

more sustained technical leadership through political transitions, enabling more consistent implementation of performance standards.

Despite these potential benefits, establishing a new entity presents significant implementation risks that could undermine reform objectives. The associated legislative processes would likely delay governance improvements for existing PPP arrangements for years. Furthermore, this approach diverges from the DoH's Plan of Action for Strengthening PPPs 2021-26, which emphasizes improving governance through existing institutional structures rather than creating new ones.

Creating a parallel structure alongside the existing PPP Node also risks institutional fragmentation and coordination challenges. A new entity would require defining clear boundaries of authority in relation to the PPP Unit, PPP Node, and other existing structures. Without careful delineation of responsibilities, this approach could complicate rather than streamline oversight of health sector partnerships, potentially creating new governance gaps rather than closing existing ones.

Option 2: Strengthening the existing PPP Node

Strengthening the existing PPP Node represents a pragmatic reform path that builds upon established governance frameworks already operating in Sindh. The Node functions within the legal structure of the 2010 PPP Act, providing an institutional foundation for the implementation of this option. This approach also aligns directly with the DoH's Plan of Action for Strengthening PPPs 2021-26, which emphasizes improving governance through existing structures rather than new ones.

Our review identified significant capacity constraints that currently limit the Node's effectiveness in managing health sector partnerships. The Node lacks dedicated legal and financial specialists necessary for complex contract design and enforcement. Performance monitoring relies largely on self-reported data without systematic verification or outcome evaluation. These gaps are particularly concerning given the Node's responsibility for contracts worth billions of rupees.

Global evidence indicates that successful PPP governance requires robust technical capacity and performance-based management approaches. The World Bank's Independent Evaluation Group (2016) identifies specialized expertise in project design, contract management, and performance monitoring as essential elements of effective PPP oversight.

Applying evidence-based principles to strengthen the Node would improve its capacity to realize value for money in outsourced services. By recruiting specialized staff and developing systematic monitoring frameworks, the Node could implement the sort of verification mechanisms that Patouillard et al. (2007) deem crucial for ensuring quality in outsourced health services. This would directly address the accountability gaps identified in PPHI's operations and grant management.

The Node's established position within departmental structures also provides distinct implementation advantages for expanding its oversight to all health sector PPP arrangements. Working through existing relationships offers a more immediate path to addressing urgent oversight needs – particularly important given the PKR 98.8 billion (US\$ 352.7 million) currently managed through inadequately monitored arrangements. Under this strengthened approach, the Node's oversight would extend beyond its current limited portfolio to include governance of PPP arrangements through PPHI Sindh and other single-line grants. Furthermore, the Node's integration within the DoH ensures that PPP governance remains aligned with broader provincial health priorities, supporting the coherent health system development that Nikolic and Maikisch (2006) identify as critical for successful health partnerships.

The principal challenge for this option lies in securing sufficient resources and operational autonomy within government structures. Transforming the Node from its current under-resourced state – with an annual budget of only PKR 28.8 million (US\$ 103,000) – would require significant investment in financial resources and human capital. Success would depend on the DoH's willingness to grant the Node greater flexibility in recruitment and operational decision-making while maintaining appropriate strategic oversight.

Reform assessment and selection

Based on our analysis against key criteria, strengthening the existing PPP Node emerged as the more viable option. Option 2 demonstrates greater implementation feasibility, avoiding the delays associated with new legislation and institutional formation required for Option 1. It also shows stronger alignment with the DoH's Plan of Action for Strengthening PPPs 2021-26, which explicitly emphasizes enhancing existing governance structures. Furthermore, Option 2 offers potential for more rapid improvement in governance outcomes by immediately addressing oversight needs while minimizing transition disruptions.

When presented with both options, the DoH concurred with this assessment and expressed a preference for strengthening the existing PPP Node. This approach maintains institutional continuity while acknowledging the need for significant capacity enhancement. The success of this reform path depends on the DoH's stewardship in empowering the Node as the focal entity for all health sector PPPs and providing the necessary resources and operational flexibility to fulfill this expanded mandate. The following section details key recommendations for strengthening the PPP Node's institutional capacity, improving service delivery networks, and enhancing quality of care through evidence-based approaches that build on global experience in PPP management.

WAY FORWARD

The strengthening of PPP governance in Sindh must address three interconnected areas: institutional capacity, service delivery networks, and quality of care. Our recommendations build on global evidence in PPP management and align with the DoH's Plan of Action for Strengthening PPPs 2021-26.

To improve institutional capacity, we recommend a systematic approach beginning with a comprehensive assessment of the PPP Node. This should include a competency assessment, review of staff surveys, and process mapping to identify specific technical and operational gaps in the PPP Node (World Bank, 2019). Building on this assessment, we propose developing a multi-pronged capacity building plan that addresses

individual skills, institutional processes, and the enabling environment through structured training programs and mentoring from PPP experts (Independent Evaluation Group, 2016). Progress should be tracked using a robust monitoring framework with clearly defined input, output, and outcome indicators, supported by regular self-assessments and external audits (Bao et al., 2020). Box 2 provides an overview of recommended functions of a restructured PPP Node.

Box 2. Proposed Functions of the Restructured PPP Node

- 1. Design and preparation of proposals, which includes conducting the need assessment, baseline, market assessment in addition to designing the model, service package, proposal, etc.*
- 2. Procurement, which includes developing guidelines on PPP standards, procedures for awarding PPPs, developing bidding documents, and carrying out transparent and competitive procurement process.*
- 3. Contract Management, which includes developing contracts for PPPs, undertaking contract management for the length of contract, and developing, promoting and facilitating PPPs while ensuring service delivery to the public.*
- 4. Monitoring, Evaluation, Accountability and Learning, which includes establishing KPIs and project goals, monitoring performance and advise necessary rectification, evaluation to extract valuable insights for quality improvement.*
- 5. Facilitation of PPPs, which includes a streamlined and structured support mechanism for private partners, enhancing private sector participation for provisions of health services through competitive partners.*
- 6. Maintain Timely and Predictable Fund Flow, which includes regular and smooth financing from the Government to the implementing partner to avoid unnecessary delays that may adversely affect service provision.*
- 7. Ensure Value for Money, which includes continuous improvement through robust M&E systems and independent studies, and attain value for money through positive health outcomes and cost efficiency.*

Strengthening service delivery networks will require evidence-based planning and clear performance targets. We recommend undertaking comprehensive geospatial mapping of all public, private, and PPP health facilities across districts to identify gaps in service delivery (Robin et al., 2019). Following this spatial analysis, the PPP Node should develop a strategic expansion plan that targets underserved districts and prioritizes essential health services, particularly reproductive, maternal, newborn, and child health interventions (Matovu et

al., 2022). The expansion strategy should also establish clear performance benchmarks for outsourced facilities, with metrics aligned to provincial indicators for access, coverage, quality, and equity (Bao et al., 2020).

Quality improvement requires strengthened regulatory collaboration and innovative financing mechanisms. We recommend collaborating with the Sindh Health Care Commission (SHCC) to integrate standardized quality assurance protocols into PPP contracts from the outset, given its statutory mandate under the Sindh Healthcare Commission Act 2013 to regulate healthcare standards and accredit facilities across the province. To drive continuous improvement, the PPP Node should consider introducing performance-based contracting tied to quality metrics. Supporting these efforts, investment in robust health management information systems is essential for systematic data collection and analysis of quality indicators, enabling evidence-based decision-making and accountability (Bao et al., 2020).

Implementation of these reforms will require strong institutional coordination and change management. Success hinges on the DoH's stewardship and effective coordination with multiple stakeholders, including PPP partners, regulatory bodies like SHCC, professional associations, civil society, and communities. Research emphasizes that clear role definition and participatory approaches are critical for successful implementation of PPP reforms (Loevinsohn and Harding, 2005; Nikolic and Maikisch, 2006).

CONCLUSION

The rapid expansion of health facility outsourcing in Sindh has outpaced the development of institutional oversight mechanisms. The PPP Node's current capacity is inadequate to effectively manage its core functions, including project identification and design, procurement, contract negotiation, and monitoring. This gap is particularly concerning given the scale of outsourcing in Sindh's health sector and the Node's crucial oversight role.

Technical expertise and financial sustainability must form the foundation of effective PPP Node reform. Market-based recruitment of professionals with specialized skills in procurement, contract

management, budgeting, and monitoring is essential. The Node requires predictable funding through planned budget allocations rather than historical incrementalism to operationalize these core functions effectively and ensure proper oversight of single-line grants.

The DoH's stewardship is crucial for successful reform implementation. As the custodian of health sector reform, the DoH must provide strategic direction and maintain oversight of publicly funded facilities and outsourced contracts (Zaidi, 2022). Through performance-based management, the DoH can ensure outsourcing initiatives align closely with provincial health priorities.

The success of these reforms depends on robust monitoring systems and effective stakeholder collaboration. The PPP Node must adopt a data-driven approach with well-defined KPIs linked to payments. Regular independent evaluation and feedback loops between service providers, the DoH, and regulatory bodies like the SHCC will be essential for maintaining quality standards and driving continuous improvement.

Strengthening the PPP Node represents more than administrative reform—it is a strategic shift toward sustainable, performance-based healthcare management in Sindh. With enhanced technical capacity, financial stability, and robust oversight, these reforms can improve the efficiency, accountability, and responsiveness of Sindh's health system, ultimately leading to better health outcomes for the province's 55.7 million residents.

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